
Goals and action plan for the National Strategy for Data Management based on the FAIR Principles – 2025

- Mandate period II, 2023-2025¹

*April 2025
Danish e-Infrastructure Consortium
DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.15281348*

¹ The mandate for period II was officially extended until ultimo December 2025, by the FAIR reference group on the 19th of February 2024

Table of Contents

1.	Introduction	4
2.	The FAIR Reference group’s overall timeline and plan for deliverables	7
3.	The FAIR working groups’ overall timeline and plan for deliverables	8
4.	Goals and actions supporting communication and knowledge exchange.....	9
	Internal and external communication:	9
5.	Premises of the working groups	10
6.	Goals and actions related to focus areas under the FAIR reference group’s working group:	
	A. Policies, tools, and research support for FAIR data management.....	11
7.	Goals and actions related to focus areas under the FAIR reference group’s working group:	
	B. Establishing FAIR infrastructure and long-term preservation.....	13
8.	Goals and actions related to focus areas under the FAIR reference group’s working group:	
	C. Financial plan for FAIR data	16
9.	Goals and actions related to focus areas under the FAIR reference group’s working group:	
	D. Plan for structuring and developing FAIR competencies and knowledge	18
10.	Goals and actions related to focus areas under the FAIR reference group’s working group:	
	E. Security aspects of FAIR data collaboration	21
11.	Goals and actions related to focus areas under the FAIR reference group’s working group:	
	F. Valuation of data	23
12.	Concluding notes	27

Terminologi/akronym	Beskrivelse
AAAI	Authentication, Authorization, and Accounting Infrastructure
CISO	Chief Information Security Officer
DeiC	Danish e-Infrastructure Consortium
DM	Data management
DMP	Data management plan
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
EU	European Union
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
IPR	Immaterielle rettigheder
PID	Persistent Identifier
TDR	Trusted Data Repository
UFS	Uddannelses og Forskningsstyrelsen
URIS	Udvalget om Retningslinjer for Internationalt forsknings- og innovationssamarbejde

1. Introduction

This action plan is one of a series of deliverables under the National Strategy for Data Management based on the FAIR principles², in the second mandate period. New readers are encouraged to visit Zenodo³ for detailed insights into the history and timeline of the Danish National Strategy for Data Management based on the FAIR principles, covering both the first and second mandated periods.

Scope of the strategy

The strategy applies to publicly funded research data, defined as the outcome of research financed by public funds or research conducted by public institutions, possibly with private funding included.

Focus areas 2025

The focus areas are largely⁴ the same from 2024, but the goals, actions and timeline differ to that of 2024.

The FAIR reference group's remit and terms of reference for this term include the current focus areas:

1. How do different disciplines implement the FAIR principles in research practices? For example, in their specific workflows, tools, etc., possibly drawing inspiration from/in collaboration with international research environments.
2. What policies and motivating/supportive measures exist to support access to and reuse of research data, including the use of Persistent Identifiers (PIDs) for digital research objects (data, software, instruments, publications, etc.)?
3. Describe best practices for data governance and policies/guidelines for overseeing overall data responsibility, even after researchers have left the institution and/or project funding has ceased.
4. What infrastructure is available for the long-term preservation (10+ years) of research data of any kind at the national level, and how is coherence and collaboration ensured between research institutions, DeiC, and the National Archives regarding long-term preservation?
5. How can services for data management planning continue to be developed nationally and internationally, and how can data management plans be made machine-readable, and be used in connection with the submission of research data to the National Archives?
6. Elaborate on how research institutions work with security infrastructure (Authentication, Authorization, and Accounting Infrastructure, AAAI) specifically and especially for sensitive data, with the aim of also making these FAIR.
7. EU programs (e.g., Horizon Europe) require grant recipients to develop data management plans in connection with grant applications. To what extent can national research funding organisations benefit from following this practice?
8. How can we ensure that research data and other electronic objects underlying published research results are stored in accordance with FAIR principles after the project ends, including at minimum a

² National FAIR-Strategy <https://www.deic.dk/da/data-management/National-FAIR-strategi>

³ [Danish National Strategy for FAIR implementation 2022](#) and [Danish National Strategy for FAIR implementation 2023-25](#)

⁴ Focus areas 8, 15, and 17 were reformulated ultimo 2024, to better fit context and development in the area. For details on the changes, please read the [annual report 2024](#). Additionally, Working Group E has renumbered the focus areas from the [original remit](#) so that focus area 14 is now 15, 15 is now 16, and 16 is now 14.

Persistent Identifier (PID) and publicly available metadata, even if the data is not openly accessible?

9. What costs related to data management can be included in budgets?
10. What competence profiles have research institutions established for the Data Stewardship research support function for researchers? How have research institutions built the data stewardship research support function for researchers?
11. To what extent is there interest in developing and offering the research support function collectively, at the national level? For example, under a central or decentralized national competence center.
12. Is there interest among research institutions in national coordination of educational offerings (not research support) within FAIR research data management? Can a potential national collaboration aim at division of labor, specialization, and joint national offerings of educational programs, such as through a competence center under the auspices of DeiC? This includes education at all levels, from bachelor to further education of scientific staff.
13. How are incentive structures or merit systems currently used nationally or internationally for FAIR data management practices at research institutions?
14. Can a better understanding be provided for the spectrum of data sensitivity? That is to say, not only personal sensitivity but also agreements, dual-use pre-prints, IPR, etc., including the researchers' own criteria for how the sensitivity of their data can be understood.
15. What are the security requirements in connection with the sharing of data?
16. In light of research groups' needs to work nationally and internationally with sensitive data, which requires strong and flexible governance, elaborate on the national and international solutions/services that can support this need.
17. What criteria for a dynamic value of data as it fluctuates through curation and changes in context are applied by local, national, and international organizations to assess the preservation rationale, economics, and sustainability thereof?

The FAIR reference group has established 6 working groups, tasked with monitoring their respective focus areas. The topics for the working groups are:

- Policies, tools, and research support for FAIR data management
With special attention to focus areas 1, 2, 3
- Establishing FAIR infrastructure and long-term preservation
With special attention to focus areas 4, 5 and 6
- Financial plan for FAIR data
With special attention to focus areas 7, 8, 9
- Plan for structuring and developing FAIR competencies and knowledge

With special attention to focus areas 10, 11, 12, and 13

- Security aspects of FAIR data collaboration
With special attention to focus areas 14, 15, 16
- Valuation of data
With special attention to focus area 17

Based on the above-mentioned focus areas, the working groups have proposed goals and actions that they consider essential for pursuing the focus areas, addressing the questions, and thus facilitating a successful implementation of the FAIR principles.

The FAIR Reference Group has also chosen to place particular emphasis on communication – both as a tool for internal collaboration between working groups and as a means of establishing a national framework for easily accessible and understandable information about the FAIR strategy and its implementation. Communication with both users and decision-makers is considered especially important, as the digitalisation of research and the national implementation of the FAIR principles represent one of the most significant practice and cultural shifts the research community has experienced in recent times.

2. Timeline and deliverables: The FAIR Reference group

Timeline	Deliverable	Elements
June 2023	The FAIR reference group is established	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Remit/ Terms of reference for the FAIR reference group is approved
September 2023	Working groups are established	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Working groups are established and relevant individuals are appointed to the groups Terms of reference for all working groups are completed
March 2024	Action plan for the goals and deliverables for 2024/25 is submitted to The Agency for Higher Education and Science	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Input for the action plan has been received by the working groups The action plan is completed and submitted to the Agency for Higher Education and Science Communication efforts have been planned
June 2024	Status meeting with the working groups	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Status on collected data and activities Status on communication with individual universities and other relevant institutions
December 2024	Annual report is submitted to The Agency for Higher Education and Science	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Status of the cross national activities received from all working groups Annual report is completed and sent to The Agency for Higher Education and Science
March 2025	Action plan for the goals and deliverables for 2025 is submitted to The Agency for Higher Education and Science	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Input for the action plan has been received by the working groups The action plan is completed, and submitted to the Agency for Higher Education and Science Communication efforts have been planned
June 2025	Status meeting with the working groups	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Status on collected data and activities Status on communication with individual universities and other relevant institutions
December 2025	Annual report is submitted to The Agency for Higher Education and Science, and recommendations are prepared	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Status of cross-national activities received from all working groups. Report to The Agency for Higher Education and Science is completed and sent. Recommendations for next steps sent to The Agency for Higher Education and Science.

3. Timeline and deliverables: The working groups

Timeline	Deliverable	Elements
Deliverable march 2024	Action plan for the goals and deliverables for 2024/25 is submitted	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Identify goals, actions, and prioritise the focus areas of the working group.
Deliverable mid 2024	Status meeting with the FAIR reference group	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Status on collected data and activities. Follow-up on the action plan and plans for additional efforts in 2024 and beyond.
Deliverable ultimo 2024	Contribution to the annual report	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Status of the cross-national activities outlined in the working group's terms of reference.
Deliverable march 2025	Action plan for the goals and deliverables for 2025 is submitted	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Identify goals, actions, and prioritise the focus areas of the working group.
Deliverable mid 2025	Status meeting with the FAIR reference group	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Status on collected data and activities. Follow-up on the action plan and plans for additional efforts in 2025.
Deliverable Ultimo 2025	Contribution to the annual report	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Status of the cross-national activities outlined in the working group's terms of reference.

4. Goals and actions supporting communication and knowledge exchange

Internal and external communication:

Goal 0.1. Communication support is established across the 6 working groups, where members can access information about:

- Policies
- Strategies
- Tools
- Manuals
- International references
- Litterature
- Courses related to FAIR and Data Management
- ...

Action 0.1: Communication channels are established for the working groups on Microsoft Teams, where members can access information about the above, save agendas, minutes, and other documents, and communicate internally.

Goal 0.2: A channel for public publishing of relevant material from the working groups and the FAIR Reference group is established.

Action 0.2: A channel on Zenodo⁵ is created for the FAIR strategy, mandate period 2023-2025.

⁵ <https://about.zenodo.org>

5. Premises of the working groups

This section has been added by the working groups, to provide an overview of the premises that need to be in place for the action plan to be successfully implemented.

- Management support from the FAIR reference group to prioritise this work at the individual universities
- Prioritisation and dedicated time from the members of working groups
- Dedicated partners/contacts from all the universities, who have the possibility to prioritise this work
- Coordination of resources among the FAIR working groups, so certain individuals/groups at the universities are not overloaded
- The working groups will develop material of guiding/observational nature, while it will be up to the FAIR Reference group to assess the extent to which the universities would fulfill the recommendations, and whether or not to follow up on them.

6. Goals and actions related to focus areas under the FAIR reference group's working group:

A. Policies, tools, and research support for FAIR data management

Working group A has developed proposals for actions that address the FAIR reference group's focus areas 1, 2, and 3.

Focus area 1:

How do different disciplines implement the FAIR principles in research practices? For example, in their specific workflows, tools, etc., possibly drawing inspiration from/in collaboration with international research environments?

Goals:

Present examples of subject-specific workflows and tools from selected disciplines across various academic fields.

Actions:

- Update the report from 2024⁶.
- Include examples from the social sciences and the humanities and describe:
 1. How do policies affect the daily work with data management and data sharing?
 2. How do we in practice collaborate?
 3. Which tools are available?
 4. What are the challenges for the discipline in relation to data sharing and policies?
- Make recommendations.

Monitoring progress, including a timeline:

Focus area 2:

What policies and motivating/supportive measures exist to support access to and reuse of research data, including the use of Persistent Identifiers (PIDs) for digital research objects (data, software, instruments, publications, etc.)?

Goals:

Collect and summarise policies and examples of motivating and supporting efforts to access and reuse research data, at universities and selected research institutions.

Actions:

Update the 2024 report.

- Analyse how the universities have worked with research IT support.
- Collect and analyse the current models for the coordination of research IT support, nationally, at the university level, at the faculty, department, research group.
- Identify challenges and make recommendations.

⁶ Krogh Kruuse, K., Grønbech Hansen, J., Hybschmann, J., Tsirigos, K., Dragsted, L. O., & Belso, R. (2025). Appendix - Working Group A – Policies, tools, and research support for FAIR data management. Report 2023-2024. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14604948>

Monitoring progress, including a timeline:

Focus area 3:

Describe best practices for data governance and policies/guidelines for overseeing overall data responsibility, even after researchers have left the institution and/or project funding has ceased.

Goals:

Identify and recommend best practices for data governance and policies to manage the overall responsibility for data. How can we foster a culture where data sharing and open science are the expected standards?

Actions:

- What needs do researchers have regarding research IT support?
- The usage of and demand for DMPs, including machine-actionable DMPs.
- Clarify how PIDs can be used to support access to and reuse of research data.
- Find examples of initiatives that strengthen data governance.
- What new policies could be introduced with the launch of DeiC Dataverse or other infrastructure?

Monitoring progress, including a timeline

7. Goals and actions related to focus areas under the FAIR reference group's working group: B.

Establishing FAIR infrastructure and long-term preservation

Working Group B has developed proposals for actions addressing the FAIR reference group's focus areas 4, 5, and 6.

Focus area 4:

What infrastructure is available for the long-term preservation (10+ years) of research data of any kind at the national level, and how is coherence and collaboration ensured between research institutions, DeiC, and the National Archives regarding long-term preservation?

Goals:

The 2024 findings of working group B identified three distinct classes of long-term research data preservation, each defined by its primary purpose. First, data preserved for **reproducibility and verification** focuses on integrity and is typically stored "as-is," ensuring it remains unchanged and accessible for audit or replication. Second, data preserved to support **future research and accessibility adheres to FAIR principles** and is deposited in Trusted Data Repositories, ensuring usability, persistent referencing, and curated availability. Lastly, data preserved for **posterity** is entrusted to national institutions like the Danish National Archives, which are responsible for its enduring logical preservation. Each approach reflects a unique preservation driver—integrity, usability, or historical continuity.

However, the findings also highlighted that roles and responsibilities concerning long-term preservation beyond reproducibility remain unclear. In response, Working Group B in 2025 will assess the maturity of current policies and infrastructures for long-term preservation, aiming to identify existing barriers and propose infrastructure for long-term preservation that promotes smooth workflows to limit the burden on researchers.

Actions:

1. **Survey the Maturity of Policies and Implementations (coordinating with Working Group A)**
 - a. Working Group B will assess the current state of long-term preservation practices among key stakeholders:
 - i. Universities
 - ii. Repositories
2. **Survey the Roles and Responsibilities Related to Key Infrastructures**
 - a. The group will map and evaluate how responsibilities are distributed across the following dimensions:
 - i. **IT Infrastructure** – Ensuring reliable bit-level preservation of FAIR-aligned data.
 - ii. **Legal and Governance Infrastructure** – Clarifying obligations and frameworks that guarantee both data accessibility and protection (coordinating with Working Group E)
 - iii. **Metadata and Semantic Infrastructure** – Supporting the long-term interpretability and meaning of data through comprehensive metadata standards.

3. Facilitate a Collaborative Workshop

- a. A workshop will be organised with participation from the Danish National Archives, DeiC, and relevant research institutions. The workshop will focus on developing synergies across organisations for the **use and interoperability of institutional and national infrastructures**. The initiative will draw inspiration from best practices in **leading European Research Infrastructures** and **Danish industries** with mature research data governance frameworks.
- b. Outcomes from the workshop will be documented and published on **Zenodo**.

Monitoring progress, including a timeline:

The group will start with actions one and two. Target for the workshop is fall 2025.

Focus area 5:

How can services for data management planning continue to be developed nationally and internationally, be made machine-readable, and be used in connection with the submission of research data to the National Archives?

Goals:

In 2024 working Group B observed that, outside of research domains with well-established standard workflows and protocols, Data Management Plans (DMPs) were often created primarily to fulfill formal requirements. In many cases, DMPs were not actively used or revised during the lifecycle of research projects. This points to a broader issue of limited practical integration between the current DMP tools and the available research data infrastructures.

Actions:

Working Group B will in 2025 assess the landscape of emerging, more actionable approaches to DMPs. The group will focus on the following actions:

1. **Map the Use of DMP Services in Denmark**
 - a. Conduct a survey of the use of DMP services in addition to DeiC DMP that are currently in use across Danish research institutions and highlight any variation in adoption, usability, or integration across domains and institutions.
2. **Monitor Developments in Europe and Denmark**
 - a. Observe and document the progress of **DMP services and tools**, with a focus on **machine-actionability** and **technical interoperability**.
 - b. Pay special attention to emerging formats such as **knowledge graphs** and the use of **Large Language Models (LLMs)** to support DMP creation and revision.
3. **Facilitate Discussion Through the Planned Workshop**
 - a. Bring findings and observations into the planned **2025 workshop** (see Action 3 under Focus Area 4) involving the Danish National Archives, DeiC, and the relevant research institutions and other relevant stakeholders.
 - b. Use the workshop to discuss the role of actionable DMPs in the broader context of long-term preservation and institutional/national infrastructure interoperability.
4. **Make recommendations** based on promising practices and lessons learned, considering alignment with national and European infrastructure efforts.

Outcomes from these activities will be summarised in a report and shared via Zenodo, contributing to the ongoing dialogue on effective data management practices in Denmark and beyond.

Monitoring progress, including a timeline:

The group will begin with Actions 1 and 2. The workshop (Action 3) is planned for fall 2025, and Action 4 will feed into the Working Group's contribution to the 2025 report.

Focus area 6:

Elaborate on how research institutions work with security infrastructure (Authentication, Authorization, and Accounting Infrastructure, AAAI) specifically and especially for sensitive data, with the aim of also making these FAIR.

Goals:**Actions:**

1. Gather information about how access to sensitive data is currently governed and how this relates to granting access in the context of handling research data in accordance with the FAIR principles.
2. Identify strategies to ensure that sensitive data can be made more FAIR, by looking mainly at EOSC deliverables.
3. Examine what is required for an infrastructure to support the governance after a dataset has been published with restricted access.
4. Gather information regarding existing solutions within academia and industry to monitor and audit data access.

Monitoring progress, including a timeline:

8. Goals and actions related to focus areas under the FAIR reference group's working group: C.

Financial plan for FAIR data

Working Group C has developed proposals for actions addressing the FAIR reference group's focus areas 7, 8, and 9.

Focus area 7:

EU programs (e.g., Horizon Europe) require grant recipients to develop data management plans in connection with applications. To what extent can national research funding organizations benefit from following this practice?

Goals:

To identify the advantages and disadvantages of a scenario where funding agencies introduce a requirement for data management plans (DMPs) and to assess the interest in developing a shared DMP-template for funding agencies implementing such a requirement. The group plans to conduct a scenario assessment to shed light on these aspects.

Actions:

1. In collaboration with Working Group A, send a questionnaire to universities, covering topics such as:
 - o Regulations and principles at universities regarding the follow-up on DMPs and FAIR principles
 - o Potential advantages and disadvantages of requiring DMPs at different stages of the project process
 - o Possible indirect effects of imposing DMP requirements
2. Develop a scenario assessment based on the hypothesis that Danish funding agencies systematically require data management plans as part of the application process.
3. Present the scenario assessment to the funding agencies.

Monitoring progress, including a timeline:

The questionnaire will be distributed in the first half of 2025. The scenario assessment will also begin in the first half of 2025 but will be completed in the second half of the year. A meeting and presentation to the funding agencies are planned for the end of 2025.

Focus area 8:

How can we ensure that research data and other electronic objects underlying published research results are stored in accordance with FAIR principles after the project ends, including at minimum a Persistent Identifier (PID) and publicly available metadata, even if the data is not openly accessible?

Goals:

This focus area will initially be addressed through a questionnaire forwarded by Working Group A. The question concerns whether researchers ensure that the above process is carried out and whether they have the necessary tools to do so.

Actions:

1. Contact the chair of Working Group A to include the question in their questionnaire, which will be distributed in the first half of 2025.

Monitoring progress, including a timeline:

Follow the work of Working Group A and jointly report on the focus area at the end of 2025.

Focus area 9:

What costs related to data management can be included in budgets?

Goals:

The working group recommends continued dialogue between universities and funding agencies regarding the lack of visibility of data management costs in budgets and financial reports. The group will explore how to best communicate its conclusions to relevant stakeholders.

Actions:

1. Investigate how the agreement between universities and funding agencies on research project funding is communicated internally at universities.
2. Develop recommendations for a more detailed specification of data management costs when discussions between Danish Universities and funding agencies resume.
3. Hold a meeting with research directors at the funding agencies to present the group's conclusions.

Monitoring progress, including a timeline:

Action 1 will be carried out in the first half of 2025, while actions 2 and 3 will take place at the end of 2025

9. Goals and actions related to focus areas under the FAIR reference group's working group: D.

Plan for structuring and developing FAIR competencies and knowledge

Working Group D has developed proposals for actions addressing FAIR Follow-up Group's focus areas 10, 11, 12, and 13. The Group has clustered the focus areas and related actions into three topics: (1) Data Stewardship, (2) National Competence Center, and (3) Recognition and Reward of FAIR Data Management. All members of the Working Group were encouraged to contribute to at least one topic.

(D1) Data Stewardship

Focus area 10:

What competence profiles have research institutions established for the Data Stewardship research support function for researchers? How have research institutions built the Data Stewardship research support function for researchers?

Goals:

- Mapping the organisational Data Stewardship landscape in Denmark
- Mapping the Data Stewardship competence landscape in Denmark

Actions:

- Investigate how research institutions have set up the local Data Stewardship research support function,
- Investigate what competence profiles research institutions have formulated for the local Data Stewardship research support function,
- Investigate how Danish universities have designed Data Stewardship education programs.

Monitoring progress, including a timeline:

- 2025: Data collection and analysis of the collected data
 - Milestone M1.1 (June 2025): Data collection & analysis (survey) and data collection (semi-structured interviews)
 - Milestone M1.2 (September 2025): Data analysis (semi-structured interviews)
 - Milestone M1.3 (November 2025): Overview of results in a report to the FAIR reference group

(D2) National Competence Center

Focus area 11:

To what extent is there interest in developing and offering the research support function collectively at the national level? For example, under a central or decentralized national competence center.

Focus area 12:

Is there interest among research institutions in national coordination of educational offerings (not research support) in FAIR research data management? Can a potential national collaboration aim at division of labor, specialisation, and joint national offerings of educational programs, such as through a competence center

under the auspices of DeiC? This includes education at all levels, from bachelor to further education of scientific staff.

Goals:

- Presentation of organisational models of a National Competence Center for FAIR Data Management,
- Presentation of potential services of a National Competence Center for FAIR Data Management,
- Overview of institutional needs and interests in relation to creating a National Competence Center for FAIR Data Management in Denmark,
- Overview of institutional needs and interests regarding national coordination of FAIR Data Management education and training in Denmark.

Actions:

- Extend the description of how existing National Competence Centers for FAIR Data Management are organized in other European countries,
- Extend the description of what kind of services existing National Competence Centers for FAIR Data Management offer in other European countries,
- Investigate whether the Danish research institutions would be interested in creating a National Competence Center for FAIR Data Management,
- Investigate whether the Danish research institutions would be interested in coordinating FAIR Data Management education and training.

Monitoring progress, including a timeline:

- 2025: Data collection and analysis of the collected data
 - Milestone M2.1 (June 2025): Data collection & analysis (desk-research & survey) and data collection (semi-structured interviews)
 - Milestone M2.2 (September 2025): Data analysis (semi-structured interviews)
 - Milestone M2.3 (November 2025): Overview of results in a report to the FAIR reference group

(D3) Recognition and Reward of FAIR Data Management

Focus area 13:

How are incentive structures or merit systems currently used nationally or internationally for FAIR data management practices at research institutions?

Goals:

- Overview of national or international recommendations on how to reward FAIR Data Management practices,
- Mapping current incentive structures for FAIR Data Management practices at Danish universities,
- Mapping current incentive structures for FAIR Data Management practices at international universities.

Actions:

- Recommendations for national initiatives regarding recognition and reward of FAIR Data Management practices

Monitoring progress, including a timeline:

- 2025: Data collection and analysis of the collected data
 - Milestone M3.1 (June 2025): Data collection & analysis (survey) and, if relevant, additional data collection (interviews or focus groups)
 - Milestone M3.2 (September 2025): Data analysis (additional data)
 - Milestone M3.3 (November 2025): Overview of results in a report to the FAIR reference group

10. Goals and actions related to focus areas under the FAIR reference group's working group: E.

Security aspects of FAIR data collaboration

Working Group E has developed proposals for actions addressing the FAIR Reference group's focus areas 14, 15, and 16. (The working group has renumbered the action areas from the remit, so that 14 is now 15, 15 is now 16, and 16 is now 14).

Stipulations for Working Group E:

At present, a significant amount of work is being conducted within the field of security at various universities—partly in connection with the Committee on Guidelines for International Research and Innovation Collaboration (URIS). Consequently, there may be considerations to take into account, such as timing data collection in alignment with this work. Additionally, this action plan must maintain a certain level of flexibility to accommodate changes, as this working group may be presented with new insights throughout the course of its work.

Scope:

The following section is not exhaustive but rather a dynamic bullet list that helps define the boundaries within which this working group operates.

- The scope of this work is limited to FAIR data—i.e., data that adhere to the FAIR principles. This means that we focus on stable/well-documented datasets rather than datasets that are still being developed, such as those created within small, local research environments in ongoing collaborations.

The intention is not to establish a separate governance framework for security but rather to explore how security considerations integrate into the governance work carried out by other working groups. This is particularly relevant for Working Group A, which is responsible for defining best practices for data governance and policies/guidelines to ensure overall data responsibility.

Focus Area 14 – data sensitivity

Can a better understanding of the various degrees of data sensitivity be provided? This includes not only personal sensitivity but also agreements, dual-use preprints, IPR, etc., including researchers' own criteria for how the sensitivity of their data can be understood.

Goals:

Mapping URIS experiences, as well as general experiences from work related to the implementation of other security measures.

Actions:

Collection of experiences from URIS implementation at Danish universities.

Monitoring progress, including a timeline:

The survey will be conducted by the end of Q3 2025.

Focus Area 15 - relevant security requirements

What are the security requirements in connection with the sharing of data?

Goals:

Contributing to the work in working groups A, B, and F.

Actions:

Selected members of the group will participate in working groups A, B, and F to contribute with the security perspective.

Monitoring progress, including a timeline:

A semi-annual review is conducted to gather solutions and challenges from the other working groups.

Focus Area 16 – approved solutions/services

In light of research groups' needs to work nationally and internationally with sensitive data, which requires strong and flexible governance, elaborate on the national and international solutions/services that can support this need.

Goals:

Assessment of universities' maturity in processes supporting vendor approval.

Actions:

A survey in the CISO-forum to investigate whether universities have established processes that have identified national or international solutions/services that can be used for sensitive data.

Monitoring progress, including a timeline:

The survey will be conducted by the end of Q3 2025.

11. Goals and actions related to focus areas under the FAIR reference group's working group: F.

Valuation of data

Working Group F has developed proposals for actions addressing the FAIR reference group's focus area 17.

Focus area 17:

What criteria for a dynamic value of data as it fluctuates through curation and changes in context are applied by local, national, and international organizations to assess the preservation rationale, economics, and sustainability thereof?

Working Group F has established the following scope parameters for its work:

1. Research data is defined as digital data collected, observed, generated, created, or reused within research activities. This encompasses digital raw data, computer code, audio and video recordings, digital texts, and detailed records of these research outputs.
2. The scope is specifically limited to research data associated with research activities conducted at Danish universities.
3. The focus is on the value of data within the context of decision-making in research data management throughout the entire research lifecycle—before, during, and after research projects at Danish universities.
4. The scope includes all stakeholders who influence or participate in these decision-making processes.

The below illustration gives a graphical overview of the framework as presented in detail in the appendices: *Appendix – Working Group F – Framework for the value of research data 2024* and *Appendix – Working Group F – Presentation on FAIR working group F – Value of research data 2024* of the Annual Report 2024 - National Strategy for Data Management based on the FAIR principles⁷.

It is important to note that this framework is not intended to function as a policy directive or an organisational instrument.

Rather, the framework will serve as the foundation for Working Group F's survey and mapping activities regarding how Danish universities apply the concept of data value. As a secondary benefit, universities may utilise the framework internally or collaboratively for data management and governance purposes, should they determine it adds value to their processes.

⁷ Renner Hansen, J., Arleth, L., Bai, B. N., Petersen, J. B., Begtrup, J., Belso, R., Boerman, S., Brinckmann, K., Buss, M., Ollerup Christensen, C., de Lichtenberg, U. N., den Boer, S., Dragsted, L. O., Falktoft, A., Fink, A. S., Friis Hansen, S., Hansen, J. G., Halvbjörn, H. H., Hansen, C. D., ... Vlachos, E. (2025). Annual Report 2024 - National Strategy for Data Management based on the FAIR principles. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14615125>

DATA VALUE

Goals:

To ensure alignment between ambition and available resources, Working Group F has categorised its' goals as primary and secondary. Secondary goals maintain equal importance but may need to be partially deferred to 2026. If certain goals cannot be achieved during the current mandate of the FAIR Reference Group, it is the hope of Working Group F that the mandate is extended for an additional two years to enable the fulfilment of all established goals.

The primary goals for 2025 are:

- Goal A: Publish a common reference library via Zotero containing scholarly papers and reports addressing data valuation within research data management and the FAIR Principles.
- Goal B: Develop and publish a foundational framework for the value of data.
- Goal C: Establish a process for framework updates and maintenance.

The secondary goals for 2025 are

- Goal D: Conduct comprehensive stakeholder interviews with representatives from Research, System administration, Funding foundations, Management and policy, and Archival institutions.
- Goal E: Produce a report analysing how data valuation informs university data management processes and how stakeholders envision the proposed framework adding value to these processes.
- Goal F: Investigate potential metrics for monitoring framework adoption and the integration of data valuation practices primarily across universities but also funding foundations and archival institutions.

Actions:

Actions supporting primary goals: Working Group F will undertake the following activities to achieve the primary goals for 2025:

- Goal A: Publish a Common Zotero Library
- Goal B: Publish a foundational framework for the value of data

- Goal C: Define a process suggestion for updating the framework

These primary goals will be accomplished through the following sequential actions:

1. Complete the "Mini Rapid Literature" review through close reading of selected articles.
2. Perform online research of selected international organisations in countries such as Australia, The Netherlands, Austria, and the United Kingdom.
3. Draft an overview report detailing the findings in action 1 and 2. This report will be published as an annex to the Annual Report 2025.
4. Conduct quality assurance and consolidation of the common Zotero library prior to its public release.
5. Develop an initial draft of the framework, appoint qualified reviewers, and publish the first version on Zenodo using a versioning strategy to facilitate future updates.
6. Formulate a maintenance plan for framework updates during the potential next mandate of the FAIR Reference Group. This plan will include an action checklist, and a risk register to identify and mitigate potential challenges.

Actions supporting secondary goals

The following activities address the secondary goals that may extend into 2026:

- **Goal D:** Conduct stakeholder interviews
- **Goal E:** Report on how the value of data informs the data management processes at the universities and how the interviewees might see the given framework bring value to the data management processes at the universities.

These goals will be addressed through:

7. Identify appropriate stakeholders for interviews by leveraging knowledge from Working Group F members, Chairpersons of Working Groups A through E, and The FAIR Reference Group.
8. Develop a comprehensive interview guide including necessary consent documentation.
9. Conduct all interview meetings, with two Working Group members present at each interview.
10. Prepare a report that synthesises interview findings with previous work conducted by the Working Group.

These activities (6-9) will commence in the first half of 2025. However, due to the complexity of coordination and the involvement of numerous individuals, completion within 2025 cannot be guaranteed.

Goal F: Explore Metrics for Framework Adoption

This new goal will be addressed last in the sequence, as insights from preceding goals will likely inform the approach to metric development for tracking framework adoption across universities, foundations, and long-term preservation institutions.

Monitoring progress, including a timeline:

Action	Estimated completion
Complete the "Mini Rapid Literature" review	April
Publication of the common Zotero library	April
Online investigation of select international organisations	June
Identify stakeholders for interviews	June
Draft an interview guide	June
Complete a first draft of the framework for review	July

Publish the first version of the framework	September
Perform interviews	Commence in September
Draft a plan for the updating of the framework	November
Annual Report 2025	November

12. Concluding notes

The FAIR Reference group and working groups acknowledge that there is overlap in the activities and will work towards effective coordination among the working groups and their focus areas. It is also recognised that the same topics can be addressed from different perspectives. Effective coordination among the chairpersons of the working groups will ensure that the focus areas are well covered from various perspectives, while avoiding too much repetition, and leaving room for potential synergies.